

THE CORRELATION BETWEEN THE PERCEPTION OF SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL AND SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE AND THEIR ADHERENCE TO THE MANAGEMENT OF ACNE

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ABSTRACT

Despite the recognized impact of acne on adolescents' psychosocial well-being, limited research has examined the direct relationship between perceived quality of life and adherence to acne management among adolescents. This study addresses this gap by investigating the correlation between perception of quality of life and adherence to acne management among students at Saint Mary's University. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study utilized standardized questionnaires to assess the students' perceived quality of life and their level of adherence to acne management practices. The results indicated that while most respondents demonstrated a high perception of their quality of life, adherence to acne management varied from moderate to high. Statistical analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between the two variables, suggesting that students with a higher perceived quality of life are more likely to consistently follow acne treatment regimens. These findings highlight the need for integrated health education programs that not only address dermatological concerns but also promote psychological well-being to enhance treatment adherence among adolescents.

Keywords: *adolescent, compliance, skin care, self-upliftment, self-esteem*

INTRODUCTION

Acne is a common dermatological condition that affects millions of individuals worldwide, with a particularly high prevalence among adolescents and young adults (Lynn et al., 2016). According to the statistical data from Bologna et al. (2012), acne vulgaris affects approximately 85% of young adults aged 12 to 25 years. Acne manifests as a multifactorial skin disorder characterized by the formation of comedones, papules, pustules, and, in severe cases, nodules and cysts (Bhate & Williams, 2013). In addition, according to Heng and Chew (2020), acne onset typically correlates with puberty; thus, prevalence rises in teenagers; and while severe acne is more common in older teenagers and males, females may experience earlier onset and higher prevalence at younger ages.

Beyond its physical manifestations, acne can have a profound impact on individuals' psychological and emotional well-being (Gallitano & Berson, 2017). Despite not being a life-threatening condition, it cannot be ignored that it has a significant influence with regards to an individual's perception of their quality of life (QoL). Previous studies have explored the association of age, gender, and acne severity with the QoL among Filipino high school students (Bernal & Sanchez, 2017). The cited studies require a deep understanding of their underlying causes, various treatment modalities, and a commitment to individualized care. By combining education, communication, and positive examples, these studies can empower young individuals to embrace their treatment plans and improve their QoL.

According to Johns Hopkins Arthritis Center, HRQoL dives into how health affects a person in their ability to live a fulfilling life. It also includes how existing diseases and treatments affect inabilities in everyday function. The study done by Tasneem et al (2023) concludes a relationship between acne severity and high plausibility of incurring depressive symptoms. Lastly, it has also been identified that there are seven main areas of HRQoL that are affected by acne: emotional functioning,

social functioning, relationships, leisure activities, daily activities, sleep, and school/work (Fabbrocini et al., 2018).

In terms of adherence, there are several factors that overlap as to how people with acne adhere to treatment or management. Hayran et al. (2021) determined two key factors: treatment regimen and patient satisfaction. Both concepts are subordinate. The treatment regimen must be able to accommodate the severity or condition of acne whilst minimizing unwanted side effects. In order to increase the possibility of adherence, the regimen should have results that satisfy the patient. Ling et al. (2023) suggest that there should be an increase in knowledge of acne and treatment among people with acne, since it has been reported that poor knowledge is the leading cause for poor adherence. Sources of knowledge regarding information on acne are also a key factor, according to Lagda et al. (2017). Family and friends were the leading sources of information, followed by the internet.

Brajaca et al. (2004) have considered increasing patient understanding to be equivalent to improved compliance, thus, a higher positive treatment effect. In addition, Lagda et al. (2017) have reviewed that there is a need to educate patients with acne to avoid misconceptions leading to inappropriate treatment. Hazarika et al. (2016) had self-consciousness as one of the criteria to measure the impact of acne on the QoL whilst considering the psychosocial domain.

Like many adolescents, Saint Mary's University Junior High School (SMU-JHS) students, namely the ninth and tenth graders, as well as the Senior High School (SMU-SHS) students, are at the age of puberty, facing the struggles of having acne. While there is a growing body of research on the psychosocial impact of acne, limited attention has been given to understanding how students perceive their quality of life in the context of acne and how this perception might correlate with their adherence to acne management. This knowledge gap is crucial since it has implications for healthcare professionals, educators, and policymakers. In relation to this, this study examined the relationship between adherence to acne management practices and perceived health-related quality of life among students at SMU Junior and Senior High School so that an intervention plan can be developed to foster self-esteem, enhance psychological resilience, and ultimately motivate students to engage more consistently in effective acne management practices.

Statement of the Problem

The general objective of the study is to investigate if there is a correlation between the perception of SMU JHS and SHS students enrolled for the school year 2024-2025, on their adherence to the management of acne and acne-related QoL. Data collection, using survey questionnaires, was conducted in February 2025, and it sought answers to the following specific problems:

1. What is the students' adherence to acne management in terms of:
 - a. age; and
 - b. biological sex?
2. What is the perception of the students on their quality of life in relation to acne?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the adherence of the respondents to acne management and their perception of quality of life?
4. What recommended self-esteem upliftment programs for people with acne can be applied?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a sequential-explanatory mixed-method design approach in determining the perceived QoL of the respondents and their adherence to acne management. This study was conducted at Saint Mary's University Junior High School Department and Senior High School

Department located in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.

The respondents were Grades 9-12 students. The sampling method utilized is stratified sampling, wherein the population is divided into distinct groups, such as age and sex. To ensure equitable representation across all year levels, further computation using proportional allocation was conducted. To be included, respondents need to bear some characteristics, like those who have experienced acne in the past, as well as those who are currently experiencing acne at the moment of data gathering. Their experiences of acne manifest enough knowledge regarding its management. Whether the acne was previously diagnosed or not, their understanding when it comes to acne management was a valuable consideration when answering the questionnaires, which supplied information needed for this study.

Table 1. *Sample size and total population per year level*

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Population Number</i>	<i>Sample number of respondents</i>
<i>JHS</i>	9	190
	10	166
<i>SHS</i>	11	455
	12	954
<i>TOTAL</i>	1765	316

Morisky Medication Adherence Scale 8 (MMAS-8) is the scale used to identify the adherence of the respondents in managing their acne according to the selected demographic criteria, particularly the age and biological sex. This study also used a modified version of MMAS-8, focusing on acne management adherence rather than merely medical treatment. For the assessment of the quality of life of the respondents with acne, the Cardiff Acne Disability Index (CADI) is utilized, which consists of 5 items. Both MMAS-8 and CADI underwent pilot testing and reliability analysis by an accredited Quantitative Data Analyst at the University Research Center of Saint Mary's University. Using Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics, MMAS-8 obtained a good internal consistency with a reliability score of 0.884. This proves that the modified version of MMAS-8 is indeed reliable in determining the adherence of the respondents to acne management. On the other hand, CADI was able to achieve a reliability score of >0.71, indicating that it has achieved an acceptable internal consistency.

The researchers coordinated with the school principal by presenting a letter addressed to the institution to allow their students to participate in the data gathering. The researchers ensured data were protected for confidentiality. Once all the data had been gathered, the researchers secured the privacy of the data. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were calculated to summarize the adherence to acne management and QoL scores among the SMU JHS and SHS students. Hypothesis testing and regression analysis were performed to investigate the relationships (Pearson-r) between QoL and acne management adherence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. Students' Adherence to Acne Management in terms of Age and Biological Sex

Table 2. *Students' Adherence to Acne Management in terms of Age*

<i>Adherence</i>	<i>14 years old</i>	<i>15 years old</i>	<i>16 years old</i>	<i>17 years old</i>	<i>18 years old</i>	<i>19 years old</i>	<i>20 years old</i>
High	0 (0%)	6 (14.63%)	54 (77.14%)	5 (6.10%)	5 (5.05%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Medium	5 (27.78%)	6 (14.63%)	11 (15.71%)	12 (14.63%)	9 (9.09%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)

Low	13 (72.22%)	29 (70.73%)	5 (7.14%)	65 (79.27%)	85 (85.86%)	2 (50%)	2 (100%)
Total	18 (100%)	41 (100%)	70 (100%)	82 (100%)	99 (100%)	4 (100%)	2 (100%)
Median	Low	Low	High	Low	Low	Low/Medium	Low

Table 2 shows the adherence to acne management among the 316 students of varying ages. Notably, adherence levels are categorized into high, medium, and low. The majority of 14-year-old students showed low adherence to acne management, which indicates significant obstacles to adherence to a prescribed routine. Noticeably, out of the 70 total 16-year-old students, 54 students (77.14%) had high adherence, 11 students (15.71%) had medium adherence, and 5 students (7.14%) had low adherence. There is a significant increase in high adherence for this age group among students compared to younger students, suggesting a relationship that maturing students are more likely to engage in acne management.

The result indicates that adherence to acne management is generally low among younger students, with a significant improvement in high adherence levels occurring at the age of 16. This progress, however, fails to be maintained in the following years as students 17 and older usually return to low levels of adherence. To support the presented results, selected respondents were interviewed to obtain supporting information regarding their adherence. A Grade 9 respondent admitted, *"May pinanghihilamos po ako na sabon na binibili ni mama. Hindi po ako sigurado kung anong brand yun.* (I use the soap that my mother buys to wash my face. I am not sure of the brand)" This indicates a possible lack of knowledge regarding exact treatments. They also mentioned, *"Opo, lalo na po kapag pagod na ako galing school o nakatulog agad* (Yes, especially if I am tired, having come from school or I have fallen asleep)." confirming forgetfulness as an obstacle. This sentiment was echoed by a Grade 10 student, *"Kapag busy sa school o kaya kapag feeling ko okay na ulit balat ko* (If I am busy in school or if I feel that my skin is great)", highlighting the effects of school obligations and the symptom self-management belief. Some students reported discontinuing their routine when they noticed their skin was getting better. As one Grade 11 student described, *"Hindi ko na po minsan tinutuloy yung routine ko kasi feeling ko hindi ko na kailangan* (I do not continue with my skin routine because I sometimes feel I do not need it anymore)." Another Grade 12 student added, *"Kapag sobrang pagod galing school or feeling ko okay nanaman like wala akong breaouts ganun po* (If I am tired, having come from school or when I see that I do not have skin breakouts)." This is an indication of a misunderstanding regarding the necessity of ongoing, long-term acne control, even when symptoms are not immediately visible. The interview also uncovered practical issues. A Grade 10 student said, *"Madalas nakakalimutan ko na dalhin lalo na pag nagmamadali po* (I often forget about it especially when I am in rush)." The cost and hassle of keeping up with a routine was also pointed out by a Grade 11 student, *"Yung consistency po madali magsimula pero mahirap panindigan. Also, yung pag-maintainbpo ng mga products lalo't pag hiyang ng face ko syemore po hindi rin mura yung mga products* (Consistency is an issue. It is easy to start with a skin routine, but to keep up with it is a challenge. Also, it is a challenge to maintain some product brands that go well with my skin because they are costly."

These results are consistent with the available literature on adherence to acne therapy. Kouotou (2022) determined that 51.3% of participants demonstrated low adherence, while Furue (2014) identified still greater rates of low adherence at 75.5%. In relation to the research conducted by Hester et al. (2015), they discovered that the adherence to acne medications was significantly lower in children than in adolescents. Specifically, only 3.71% of children and 13.38% of adolescents were considered in compliance. This corroborates the observed trend of low adherence among younger students and modest improvement among older adolescents.

Table 3. *Students' Adherence to Acne Management in terms of biological Sex*

Adherence	Male	Female
High	10 (7.69%)	11 (5.91%)
Medium	7 (5.38%)	38 (20.43%)
Low	113 (86.92%)	137 (73.66%)
Total	130 (100%)	186 (100%)
Median	Low	Low

Table 3 shows the data comparing adherence to acne management between 130 total male and 186 total female students. The entire group of 113 males, representing 86.92%, demonstrated low adherence, suggesting that the majority deal with difficulties adhering to prescribed acne management protocols. In contrast, female students demonstrated slightly improved adherence measures, with 11 students, representing 5.91%, achieving high adherence, and 38 students, accounting for 20.43%, classified as having medium adherence. This indicates that, irrespective of biological sex, a significant proportion of students are not adequately following their acne management, underscoring the necessity for targeted interventions to enhance adherence among adolescents. As stated by a female respondent during the interview, "*Kapag may assurance po na safe gamitin yung pangskin care routine o kahit sabon po* (If there is assurance that the skincare product or soap is safe to use)" when asked what would help them to take better care of their skin. With the same question, a male respondent answered "*Kapag pinasimple siguro yung steps. Ang hirap kasing intindihin yung gamit ng mga products. Complicated siyang sundan kaya minsan nakakatamad din* (Maybe if the step is simplified. It's quite a challenge to comprehend the usage of the products. They can be so complicated that I feel lazy to do them)." This implies that some factors affecting the adherence of the female respondents are side or adverse effects, while for male students, it is the complexity of management.

In the study of Moradi Tuchayi et al. (2016), they discussed the problems associated with acne treatment adherence, including lack of knowledge, confusion about usage, weak physician-patient relationships, fear of adverse reactions, and cost. Moreover, they also discussed solutions such as treatment simplification, technology, and dynamic education. They emphasized that recognizing these problems and finding appropriate solutions is crucial for achieving successful treatment outcomes.

Table 4. *Students' Adherence to Acne management from Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8)*

Statements	F (x) of YES	Percent
1. Do you sometimes forget to do your routine care or take your prescribed medication for the management of acne?	79	25.00
2. People sometimes fail to carry out their acne management practices for reasons other than forgetting. Thinking over the past 2 weeks, were there any days when you did not perform your acne management practices?	97	30.70
3. Have you ever cut back or stopped performing management practices because you felt worse when you took it?	124	39.24
4. When you travel or leave home, do you sometimes forget to bring along your supplies such as skin care products for acne management?	141	44.62
5. Did you perform all your management practices yesterday?	209	66.14
6. When you feel like your symptoms are under control, do you sometimes stop doing your management practices?	140	44.30
7. Performing management practices every day is real inconvenience for some people. Do you ever feel hassled about sticking to your management plan?	124	39.24
8. Do you have difficulty remembering to perform all your management practices for acne?	159	50.32

Table 4 shows the students' adherence to acne management from the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale. Furthermore, 97 students, corresponding to 30.70%, indicated that there were instances in the past two weeks when they did not engage in their acne management practices for reasons besides mere forgetfulness, suggesting that additional factors may influence their non-adherence. A total of 124 students, corresponding to 39.24%, reported reducing or discontinuing their management practices because of adverse effects encountered concerning their management of acne, emphasizing that negative acne treatment experiences may hinder their continuing adherence. Practical challenges are evident with 141 students, representing 44.62%, indicating that they forgot to bring their skincare products while traveling or leaving home. Despite all of this, a majority of 209 students, representing 66.14%, completed all their management practices the previous day, indicating that adherence is attainable, at least in the short term. Nevertheless, 140 students, representing 44.30%, reported ceasing their management practices once symptoms appeared manageable, highlighting concerns regarding the premature cessation of treatment. Likewise, 124 students, representing 39.24%, indicated having the feeling of inconvenience and hassle with their daily management routine, while 159 students, or 50.32%, reported difficulties in remembering to complete all their practices. This indicates the need for supportive strategies to improve adherence and aid in acne management.

Snyder et al. (2014) found that forgetfulness was the primary reason individuals failed to adhere to their acne treatment plans. This aligns with the current study's findings, where 25% of students reported forgetting to take their medication or perform their regular skin care routine. Additionally, side effects were identified by Snyder et al. as another major factor influencing non-adherence, which corresponds with the 39.24% of students who reduced or discontinued treatment because they felt worse after using their medication. Similarly, Modarres Tuchayi et al. (2016) highlighted the importance of addressing practical barriers and simplifying treatment regimens to enhance patient adherence. This supports the results from the fourth statement, in which 44.62% of students admitted to forgetting their skin care products when traveling, and the seventh statement, where 39.24% reported feeling stressed by their daily routines, both of which can negatively affect treatment consistency.

The findings reveal that adherence to acne management varies according to age and biological sex, with certain age groups and sexes demonstrating a higher adherence rate. In nursing practice, this suggests the need for age and gender-specific educational interventions.

Section 2. Perception of the Students on their Quality of Life in relation to Acne

Table 5. Perception of the Students on their Quality of Life in Relation to Acne

	Frequency	Percent
Minimally Impaired	128	40.5
Mildly Impaired	122	38.6
Moderately Impaired	56	17.7
Severely Impaired	10	3.2
Total	316	100.0

Mean: 4.68 (Mildly Impaired) Std. Dev. :3.345

Table 5 presents the perception of students regarding their quality of life in relation to acne. Among the 316 respondents, a significant portion, 128 students or 40.5%, reported being minimally impaired by acne, indicating that while they may experience some issues, their overall quality of life remains largely unaffected. The overall mean score of 4.68, categorized as "mildly impaired," along with a standard deviation of 3.345, suggests that while many students experience some level of impairment, the majority do not view their acne as greatly affecting their quality of life.

Alasbi et al. (2021) stress that students' quality of life is greatly impacted by acne, according to their findings, with those who suffer from severe acne reporting the lowest quality of life scores. This implies that acne can affect people differently, but it can have a major impact on their general health, especially for those who have more severe cases. The present study disagrees with this result due to the majority of the perception of QoL being minimally impaired, reflecting the low impact of acne.

Table 6. *Students' Perception on their Quality of Life in relation to Cardiff Acne Disability Index (CADI)*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Description
1. As a result of having acne, during the last month have you been aggressive, frustrated or embarrassed?	1.07	.894	A little
2. Do you think that having acne during the last month interfered with your daily social life, social events or intimate personal relationships?	.92	.807	A little
3. During the last month have you avoided public changing facilities or wearing swimming costumes because of your acne?	.63	.864	A little
4. How would you describe your feelings about the appearance of your skin over the last month?	1.09	.872	A little
5. Please indicate how bad you think your acne is now:	.97	.766	A little

Table 6 reveals the impact of acne on students' emotional and social experiences over the past month, as indicated by mean scores and standard deviations for various statements.

The qualitative descriptions show that, while students recognize certain emotional and social repercussions of acne, these effects are largely regarded as minor. Nevertheless, this demonstrates the importance of supportive interventions that address both the physical and emotional aspects of living with acne. In the study of Morshed et al. (2023), while AV can negatively affect individuals' psychological well-being, self-esteem, and quality of life (QoL), the severity of these impacts can vary greatly among individuals. The study shows that students' perception of their quality of life is significantly affected by acne, impacting their emotional well-being and social interactions.

Section 3. Correlation between the Adherence of the Students to Acne Management and their Perception of Quality of Life

Table 7. *Significant Relationship between the Adherence of the Students to Acne Management and their Perception of Quality of Life*

MMAS8	Pearson Correlation	-.329**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	316

Legend: Pearson r.: Qualitative Description; Very High Correlation: 0.99+ – 0.80+, High Correlation 0.79+ – 0.60+, Moderate Correlation 0.59+ – 0.40+, Low Correlation 0.39+ – 0.20+, Very Low Correlation: 0.19+ – 0.01+

Table 7 shows the Pearson correlation coefficient of -.329, which signifies a low positive correlation between adherence to acne management and the perception of quality of life. This indicates that respondents who adhere more closely to their acne management regimen tend to report a slightly better quality of life. Furthermore, adherence to acne management alone may not be a strong predictor of quality of life. While acne management adherence may contribute to a more positive quality of life perception, other factors likely play a substantial role and should be further investigated.

The results are supported by the study of Jones-Caballero et al. (2008), emphasizing that following acne therapy was connected to higher subjective severity ratings and better Skindex-29

results, a skin disease assessment tool, hence improving the quality of life. This underlines the need of treating both the physical and psychological components of acne management since treatments that encourage adherence to therapy can greatly improve people's general well-being. A significant positive correlation exists between adherence to acne management and perceived quality of life. This finding implies that improving adherence can directly enhance students' well-being.

Section 4. Recommended Self-Esteem Upliftment Program for Students with Acne

Based on the results and findings, the recommended program will carry a one- to two-day forum that concerns the significance of acne operation with respect to both physical and emotional well-being. Dermatologists and healthcare professionals will give substantiation-grounded information on acne, its causes, and treatment options, stressing the significance of thickness in skincare routines and medical treatments. To further engage scholars, the program will include a validation from a speaker who has *tête-à-tête* suffered from acne and faced the emotional and social challenges associated with it. This speaker will discuss ways in which successful acne operation appreciatively affects their quality of life and encourages scholars to remain married to their treatment. Through this admixture of educational accoutrements, professional recommendations, and individual experience, the self-upliftment program aims to enhance adherence to acne operation, increase awareness on the impact of skin health on daily life, and empower students to take control of their health and well-being.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The findings revealed that adherence levels were predominantly low across different age groups and sexes, with the highest adherence observed among the 16-year-olds. Both male and female students exhibited low overall commitment to acne routines, with females showing slightly better medium adherence. Despite these low adherence levels, most student reported only minimal to mild impairment in their quality of life caused by acne, suggesting a general resilience but also an underlying need for better support.

A significant but low negative correlation was found between adherence and perceived quality of life, indicating that those who manage their acne more consistently tend to experience slightly better well-being. This emphasizes the importance of early, age-appropriate education on acne care, the simplification of skin care routine, and interventions that address both physical treatment and emotional support.

This study has potential limitations. The sample selected for this study was specifically students who have either experienced acne in the past or are currently experiencing acne. This includes those who acquire pimples from time to time. The results obtained may not reflect directly on those who are currently suffering from acne vulgaris, therefore, they lack direct representation for those suffering from long-term acne.

Recommendations

For the researchers in the future who wish to carry out a similar study, it is suggested that they broaden the population by incorporating students from various schools or areas in order to achieve a broader and more diverse set of results. It would also be beneficial to look at other variables that may influence adherence and quality of life, such as socioeconomic status, the kind of acne management or treatment being used, the mental health of those who have acne, and where students

are obtaining information about acne. Conducting a longitudinal study rather than a cross-sectional survey would also be useful in observing how adherence and perceptions evolve. Focusing and strengthening the qualitative component rather than the quantitative component of the study through focus group interviews or more extensive interviews may offer more individualized information and increased understanding of the experiences of those living with acne. Future investigators are also challenged to design and evaluate targeted interventions, such as educational programs or support groups, to empower students to better control their acne and feel more confident. Engaging the parents and healthcare providers may provide additional insight regarding the predictors of treatment compliance. It is also recommended that the survey instruments be translated to enhance their comprehensibility to Filipino students, allowing a better representation of the results. Employing digital instruments such as reminder applications can also be an option to assist in consistency in acne care. These advances may assist subsequent research in achieving even better outcomes and designing better solutions for students with acne.

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